

Conductometric Study of some 1 : 1 Salts in Ethanol-H₂O and Glycerol-H₂O Mixtures at 25⁰

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The association of ions in solvents of low dielectric constants and in water-rich mixtures of high dielectric constants to form ion-pairs is considered at present as an accepted fact¹. Such an ion-pair can exist for a sufficiently long period of time to act as kinetic unit in collision with the molecules of the solvent. Dielectric constant², hydrogen bond³ and temperature⁴ are parameters which affect on the ion-pair formation besides the size of both anion and cation⁵.

The present work deals with the study of the effect of hydrogen bonding effect on the association phenomena in sodium formate, sodium acetate and sodium benzoate at 25⁰ using conductance measurements. Such hydrogen bonding is expected to be greater in glycerol-H₂O mixtures as compared with that of ethanol-H₂O. The ratios were adjusted in both the mixtures for obtaining ethanol-H₂O and glycerol-H₂O with the same dielectric constant (dielectric constants of 20% glycerol-H₂O and 10% ethanol-H₂O are 72.8 and 72.9, respectively). Also the effect of the size of the anion on the association of the three organic sodium salts has been discussed.

Results and Discussion

Viscosity and dielectric constant data⁶ of ethanol-water and glycerol-water are presented in Table 1. In the solutions, the following ionic equilibrium is considered,

where X is formate, acetate or benzoate.

The conductometric data were treated by the Fuoss and Kraus method⁷, where the following equation is applicable,

$$F(Z)/\Lambda = 1/\Lambda_0 + K_A/\Lambda_0.c \Lambda_f^2/F(Z) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where, } Z = (A + B \Lambda_0/\Lambda_0^{3/2}) \sqrt{c} \Lambda, \quad (3)$$

here A and B are the Onsager constants, Λ and Λ_0 the equivalent and the limiting equivalent conductance, respectively. An approximate estimate of Λ_0 is first made by extrapolating the experimental data of Λ against $\sqrt{c}$. The ion activity coefficient (f) of Na⁺ was estimated by the Debye-Hückel approximation,

$$-\log f = 0.509 \sqrt{c}$$

where, c is the concentration (mol dm⁻³).

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY (η), DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D) AND ONSAGER CONSTANTS (A, B) FOR 10% ETHANOL-H₂O AND 20% GLYCEROL-H₂O MIXTURES AT 25⁰

Parameter	10% Ethanol-H ₂ O	20% Glycerol-H ₂ O
η (poise)	1.323	1.542
D	72.80	72.90
A	0.256 539 939	0.256 012 2
B	0.423 264 184	0.362 901 6

TABLE 2—VALUES OF Λ_0 , $\Lambda_0 \eta$ AND ASSOCIATION CONSTANT (K_A) SODIUM FORMATE, SODIUM ACETATE AND SODIUM BENZOATE AT 25⁰ IN 10% ETHANOL-H₂O AND 20% GLYCEROL-H₂O MIXTURES

Solvent	Salt	Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	$\Lambda_0 \eta$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ poise	K_A M^{-1}
10% Eth-H ₂ O	Formate	76.290	100.93	133.59
	Acetate	72.194	95.51	209.98
	Benzoate	61.955	81.97	185.95
20% Gly-H ₂ O	Formate	81.179	125.18	144.59
	Acetate	66.767	102.95	561.85
	Benzoate	44.632	68.82	258.44

It is seen from equation (2) that the plot of $F(Z)/\Lambda$ against $c\Lambda_f^2/F(Z)$ should be a straight line; the slope being equal to K_A/Λ_0^2 and the intercept $1/\Lambda_0$. Then K_A and Λ_0 can be evaluated. In order to obtain the requisite plot, an approximate estimate of

Λ_0 is first made by extrapolating the experimental data of Λ against $\sqrt{c}$ and from this a tentative result for Z is derived by means of equation (3), since A and B can be calculated from the viscosity and the dielectric constant of the solutions. In this way a preliminary value of $F(Z)$ is obtained which can be employed in equation (2). The results are then plotted as required by equation (2) and the datum for Λ_0 as obtained may then be employed to calculate $F(Z)$ more accurately. The final results will not significantly be affected by a small error in the provisional values of Λ_0 and so it will not be necessary to repeat the calculations more than once or twice.

As shown in Table 2, the Λ_0 values for the above three salts decrease according to the following order : formate > acetate > benzoate. This is true in the two solvents : 10% ethanol-H₂O and 20% glycerol-H₂O mixtures. But for each salt, Λ_0 values in ethanol-H₂O are larger than that in glycerol-H₂O mixture (except for sodium formate). To explain this behaviour (with the exception of sodium formate), we find that intramolecular hydrogen bonding is expected to be greater in glycerol than in ethanol. Such intramolecular hydrogen bonding must be retarding the mobility of the ions resulting in a decrease of the equivalent conductance values for the same salt in glycerol-H₂O mixture than in ethanol-H₂O mixture. However for the exception for sodium formate can be explained as follow. The acid of formate (formic acid) has a different behaviour of the corresponding aliphatic organic series of acids, due to the fact that it has more aldehydic character than acidic one in some of its behaviour.

There is a common characteristic in Walden products, $\Lambda_0\eta$ (the product of the limiting equivalent conductance Λ_0 , and viscosity of the solvent η) that, the $\Lambda_0\eta$ values for the three salts in the two solvents decrease in the order : formate > acetate > benzoate. The degrees of decrease in $\Lambda_0\eta$ are small in ethanol-H₂O mixture; about 9% decrease on going from formate, acetate to benzoate, but it is about 30% in glycerol-H₂O for the same series. It is obvious that $\Lambda_0\eta$ decreases with increasing the size of anion. This

decrease may probably be interpreted as a result of solvation of the anion and hydrogen bonding formation which is recommended in glycerol-H₂O than in ethanol-H₂O.

Inspection of the data of Table 2 shows that the association constants (K_A) generally increase in the order : formate < benzoate < acetate. The lack of association found for formate in comparison with the other two salts is due to the fact that each two ions of formate are bonded by intramolecular hydrogen bonding (exist as dimer). The structure of this dimer is

The formation of this dimer will decrease the probability of association between sodium and formate. When a compound containing O-H linkage (as in case of acetate) can not undergo intramolecular hydrogen bonding, more association by intermolecular hydrogen bonding will almost always occur. This is most likely the reason behind the higher values of K_A for acetate over the benzoate salts.

It has been found that there is a close relationship between the K_A values and the strength of solvation of anion, that is, the stronger the anion (formate) is solvated, the weaker the association between sodium and formate becomes in ethanol-H₂O mixture. Although the dielectric constants of ethanol-H₂O and glycerol-H₂O are in the same range ($D \approx 72.8$), all salts are less associated in ethanol-H₂O than in glycerol-H₂O mixtures. The difference between two K_A values for each salt is too much, in spite of the dielectric constants being in the same range of value. This difference is due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding effect where glycerol is more hydrogen bonded than ethanol. The intermolecular hydrogen bonding between glycerol and acetate ion is stronger causing higher association than in case of ethanol and acetate ion. Therefore, the values of K_A for the three salts are larger in glycerol-H₂O than in ethanol-H₂O mixtures.

It is well accepted that the extent of ion association in the three salts solutions depends on the nature of the ion-solvent interaction which takes place in the solution rather than being dependent on the dielectric constant of the medium⁸. The fact that supports this conclusion is the choice of the ratios of glycerol-H₂O and ethanol-H₂O mixtures having the same dielectric constant.

Experimental

Sodium formate, sodium acetate and sodium benzoate were of A.R. grade. The individual stock solution was standardised by ion-exchange procedure. Glycerol⁹ and ethanol¹⁰ were purified by standard methods. Deionised distilled water was used for dilution.

Conductance was measured using a LBR conductivity meter equipped with a LTA 100 cell. Full details concerning equipment and technique have been outlined elsewhere¹¹. The conductance of the above three salts was measured in 10% ethanol-H₂O and 20%

glycerol-H₂O mixtures at 25° in a concentration range up to 10⁻³M.

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